

Electronic Resources Use and Access Pattern

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Abstract

In today's rapidly changing world, the information needs of learners and knowledge seekers are met through a plethora of sources. The digital resources available in a library play a prominent role in facilitating access to required information to the users in an easy and expeditious manner. The library is a repository of resources that create a fundamental change in education. Adequate electronic resource facilities empower and enrich the higher education system in meeting the best academic needs. Users can access e-resources either by local or remote locations. The electronic resources available in a library play a vital role in facilitating access to required information to the users in an easy and expeditious manner. The resources namely CD-ROM, online Journals, Online books, OPAC and the internet are slowly replacing the importance and usage of print media. In this paper, we discuss electronic resources like CD-ROM, electronic books, online journals, etc., access pattern, uses and advantages & disadvantages of e-resources.

Keywords: e-Resources, e-Documents, e-Book, e-Journal e-Images, e-Audio/visual resources.

Introduction

The twentieth century was shaped by sweeping changes in communication technologies. The emergence and use of information technology is the century's most significant development affecting scholarly communication. The application of computers to information processing has brought several products and services to the scenes. Consequently, the academic community has undergone tremendous changes during these years, assuming new dimensions influenced by technology-driven applications. Libraries have witnessed a great metamorphosis in recent years both in their collection development and in their service structures.

We enabled services are provided through the library web page. New services include access to internet and internet-based tools and services, access to electronic information sources and digital library of local and institutional documents. Journals, books, dissertation and theses, course material and patents are some important sources of information that are now available in electronic form.

Electronic Resources

Electronic resources are the electronic representation of information. There are available in various forms like e-books, digital libraries, online journal magazine, e-learning tutors and on line test. Because of the effective presentation with multimedia tools, these e-resources have become the source of information. Electronic resources deliver the collection of information as full-text databases, e-journals, image collections, multimedia in the form of CD, tape, internet, web technology, etc. E-resources may include e-journals, e-discussions, e-news, data archives, e-mail on line chatting, etc. can be called as e-resources. Electronic information source is a wide range of products going from electronic periodicals to CD-ROMs, from the mailing list to databases, all of them having a common feature of being used and some time modified by a computer

Electronic Resources Definition

Electronic resources are defined as “Any publication available resources, which can be accessed via computer. These include commercially produced resources such as bibliographic databases, electronic reference books, search engines for full-text collections, digital collections of data and data sets, as well as resources have been made freely available on the internet, whether specifically to higher educational institutions or to the public in general”.

Electronic information may be broadly defined as “The information stored in a medium, which requires an electronic device to read /access its contents.” Information stored in different electronic media such as Floppies, Magnetic tapes, CD-ROMs/ DVDs, flash/pen drives, Hard Disk, OPAC, Online documents including online journals, etc. Electronic information had resources promised and continue to promise still a revolution in its availability and easy access. Although, it seems to most practitioners that we are in the mid-revolution and electronic resources have already become part of the naturally established order of things for researchers in developed countries.

Need For Resources

E-Resources enable the librarian to provide better services to the user community. The few considerable points are mentioned bellow:

- To get access to an information source by the more than one users.
- E-Resources can be searched quickly
- These can be found easily by the user
- These resources can be stored in a huge amount
- Amount of time on the e-Resources use
- Analysis of the purpose of e-Resources by respondents
- Know different types of e-Resources commonly used by respondents
- To collect, store, organize information in digital form
- To promote efficient delivery of information economically to all the users
- To encourage co-operative efforts to save and share the investments in research resources, computing and communication networks.

Types of Electronic Resources

The following are the most frequently encountered types are:

- e-Journals
- e-Books
- ETD's (Electronic Theses and Dissertations)
- Electronic databases
- E-Reference databases (biographies, dictionaries, directories, encyclopedias, etc.)
- OPACs

E-Journals

Electronic journals appeared during 1970's but became popular in late 90's. e-Journals are periodical literature that is made available as individual titles via an electronic medium, typically the World Wide Web. E-Journals have now become a major source of information delivery for scholars and researchers. There are many Open Sources e-Journals available through the Internet. Some Library and Information Science Open Source E-Journals and their URLs. Today most of the journals appear as a parallel version of their print counterparts. E electronic journals could be accessed through Gopher, Ftp, Telnet and E-mail but are namely accessed through the web.

E.Books

An e-Book is essential to the contents of books distributed in the form of an electronic file. Any file that holds text can be in theory used as an e-book. However, there are several specialized formats and reading programmes designed with e-books reading in mind. e-Books are exactly like print or paper books except that they are bound electronically. e-Books come in a variety of formats as well. They can be downloaded in .pdf, HTML, plain text and rich text formats

Electronic Theses and Dissertations

An ETD is a document that explains the research or scholarship of a research scholar in an electronic format. It is simultaneously suitable for machine archives and worldwide retrieval. The ETD provides a technologically advanced medium for expressing the scholar's ideas. One can prepare an ETD by using nearly any word processor or document preparation system and by incorporating relevant multimedia objects. ETDs are made available to anyone that browses the World Wide Web. They consume virtually no library shelf space, and never collect dust.

Electronic database

Data that is store more or less permanently in a computer readable field is termed as database. A Database can also be seen as a collection of interrelated largely similar data or data records in a set of linked cites designed to facilitate the retrieval of information, which may be processed by one or more application programmes.

Library catalogs

Most libraries now provide access to their catalogs forms their web sites; Many others provide information about their holdings into larger databases such as World Cat or the RLG Union Catalog. The library provides links to these catalogs under the ' catalogs' section on its web site.

E-Reference databases (biographies, dictionaries, directories, encyclopedias, etc.)

E - Reference databases such as e-dictionaries, e-encyclopedias, e-almanacs, e-atlases, etc. are research tools that can help you with your paper or project. Reference sources provide answers to specific questions, such as brief facts, statistics, and technical instructions; provide background information, or direct you to additional information sources.

OPAC

OPAC is a term used to describe any type of computerized library catalog. It allows in providing the flexibility to:

- Find out what the library has to offer
- Check the status of an item

- Check the library record for fines, reserves, or over dues
- Reserve the item
- Look up community information
- Link up with library catalogs or databases in other communities

E-Newspapers

Electronic News resources like Lexis Nexis and Factiva, and links to local, national, and international newspapers.

E-Mail

Email is shorthand term meaning Electronic-mail. Email much the same as a letter, only that it is exchanged in a different way

Image Databases (Art, Maps, etc.)

Some databases include graphics or images, such as photos, paintings or maps. You can use the Database Finder page to locate these. The Art Subject Guide also provides extensive information about locating images,

Characteristics of Resources

The following are the characteristics of Electronic Information:

- Potentially E-Resources are huge
- Encompassing every thing
- Organized arbitrarily
- Occupying no physical space
- Full content searchable
- Elimination of time, space, cost constraints
- The public domain of information (Internet)
- Hyperlinks to related information
- Preservation & Dissemination of knowledge
- Faster and wider
- Backup preservation
- Archiving the content
- User can get anywhere his required information from e-documents
- More than one person can read e-documents at the same time
- Any revision and correction can easily be done

How to Access Electronic Resources

For full access to our electronic journals, databases and e-books you must be a member of the College and have an Imperial ICT account.

On-Site Access

If you are at an Imperial College London campus, most e-resources can be accessed directly (there is no requirement to enter a username and password).

A few e-resources do require a username and password. If so, a note on Library Search “Details” tab states “Access requires a specific username and password.” You can find the password on our Password list.

Off-Site Access

Most of our e-resources can be accessed off-site, allowing you to work from home or another location. There are three methods of off-site access:

- Using the “View It” tab in Library Search - when prompted, log in with your College Username and password
- UK Federation / Institutional login - use your College username and password to log in to e-resources
- Virtual private network (VPN) - connect to the College VPN to allow you to access e-resources as if you were on-site

Advantages of Electronic Resources

- E-Resources allow interactive facility and allow interaction between author, publisher and users
- The data can be easily manipulated at regular intervals and can always be kept up-to-date in electronic media.
- High speed and efficiency benefits the publish distributing journals electronically
- The electronic resources indifferent to environment hazards and if handled with care will show great durability which cannot be achieved on paper-based print media.
- In contrast to print media, electronic media minimizes space, time and cost of maintenance at the longer run.
- Multiple access and local networks become easy.
- Cost of publication and distribution is less than the print versions.
- It saves time easy to search.

Disadvantages of E-Resources

- Initial high infrastructure and high installation cost.
- Need special equipment to access.
- Lack of compatibility among different publishers.
- Hardware and software compatibility issues between publishers and users.
- Excessive printing of documents.
- The difficulty inherent in relating to a large amount of data on a screen.
- Causes more concern about copyright.
- Efficient manpower is required.

Conclusion

e-Resources help the readers to collect the information in a very short time. It is the need of time to change the traditional librarian to the techno-crack librarian.e-resources helping a lot for the research wor.

In recent years, there has been a phenomenal growth of electronic journals. In many consortiums, a large number of electronic journals are hosted which outnumber other electronic resources. The impact of electronic journals in the academic world is phenomenal, leading to wide spread availability of them. The digital environment offers new opportunities for cooperative action in making information available to users. However, the shift to a predominantly digital environment will occur at different rated in different fields.

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